

THE ADVANTAGE OF MARKET RESEARCH IN MARKETING ACTIVITIES OF TEXTILE ENTERPRISES UNDER GLOBAL COMPETITION

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Abstract. *This article examines new development ways of improving marketing services and their implementation and improving production and sales strategies, as well as developing branding policies, raising the goal of exporting enterprises to the level of a national brand.*

Keywords: *enterprise, competition, market, competition, demand, product, brand, customer.*

INTRODUCTION. In the conditions of global competition, the success of any company largely depends on marketing activities. Modern marketing requires the acquisition of these customers, their increase, and the implementation of goods and services taking into account and adapting to market opportunities. In the conditions of a competitive market, in accordance with the principles of enterprise marketing, all aspects of economic activity should be planned and implemented taking into account market requirements and consumer needs. It should be said that the efficiency of production and sales of modern enterprises depends on the variety and quality of manufactured goods, their penetration into sales markets, operations creating scale-optimized production is all a result of using marketing.

Today, in order to effectively organize their activities, textile enterprises in the business sector are implementing new ways of development and measures to improve marketing services and their implementation, as well as to improve production and sales strategies, as well as to develop branding policies. In the following years, the export volume is increasing at the expense of many enterprises producing food, clothing, and textile products. For this purpose, the goal of exporting enterprises - the task of raising their products to the level of a national brand - is one of the most urgent issues.

The brand helped distinguish many of the features that were important to the consumer and made the product easier to understand. Products and services have been replaced by brands with specific values and impressions for consumers.

Branding is the process of embedding information about products or services in the minds of consumers or creating an impression on potential customers about the product or service. It is important to consider customer mindset in product advertising. To make a positive impression, it is necessary to choose the right brand name, to pay special attention to the visual effects in the logo, and to give specific information about the product. A brand is a name, term, symbol or image, or a combination of these elements, intended to identify the goods or services of a specific manufacturer, as well as to differentiate them from the products of competitors.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. A brand is a unique name, symbol, design or image used to identify a specific product or company. A brand is a combination of product characteristics: its name, packaging, price, history, reputation, advertising method. The brand helps in:

1. Product identification, that is, the product should be recognized as soon as it is touched.
2. Separation from competitors' products, that is, separation of the product from the total mass.

Branding can also be defined as the process of creating and developing a brand.

A consumer does not like a brand or a product, he only loves himself, and this brand is what boosts his ego, his self-esteem.

Consumer brand loyalty allows manufacturers to:

- to keep their customers even in the deteriorating macroeconomic situation;
- easily overcome the consequences of the crisis in the country, industries, enterprises;
- sell products at high prices.

A properly established relationship between goods and consumers allows to significantly reduce the costs of mutual agreements.

Intensification of competition between manufacturers requires expanding the possibilities of achieving the production of products that meet international quality standards, more in-depth study of the population's demand for high-quality and modern design products, and an increase in the product range.

One of the main problems in the product market is the fact that the products produced by enterprises without having a sufficient market brand or reputation are causing a decrease in the demand for the product. A reasonable way to avoid such problems is to implement new methods of the most modern and improved marketing research in market research.

In the process of researching the market, goods, consumers, competitors, the amount of products that can be sold, the characteristics of the goods, the group of consumers, the competitiveness of the enterprise and its place in the market, the organization of advertising and the desire of buyers are determined. By researching the textile market from the point of view of marketing, it aims to adapt the manufactured goods to the high demands of the market and the consumer, the possibility of effective sale of goods, new segments for its expansion, improvement of quality, creation of reserves and new goods, meeting consumer demand and obtaining high profit. This should be done on the basis of highly profitable, competitive activity of the enterprise.

Marketing research presents a set of tasks that must be solved. Taking into account the constantly changing situation, the influence of a variety of factors, the potential of different firms, certain research tasks set before the firm's marketing service leads to diversity.

The task of marketing research is to achieve predictability of market behavior. One of the most important stages of marketing research is the development of a research plan. In this, the sources, methods, tools, selection procedures and plans for collecting the data and information necessary for the research will be drawn up. The data and sources on which the research is based can be used and processed several times in relevant fields. In conclusion, it can be said that in the context of the development of the innovative and digital economy, by conducting marketing research in the development of the textile industry and developing its strategies based on this, creating a wide range of national goods with high added value in the economy in the domestic and foreign markets.

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